

ARTEMIS

Communication Plan

Deliverable D6.1

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Introduction

Society increasingly appreciates the agro-ecological systems as a help to address some issues caused by existing intensive agricultural systems, and modern crises such as climate change, soil depletion, water scarcity, biodiversity loss and malnutrition. The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project is focused on the role of agro-ecological practices in soils' ability to mitigate and abate climate change and it combines an integrated approach based on long-term data, numeric modelling, literature survey and targeted field measurements with or by practitioners. Close contact with practitioners in the field is essential for rapid implementation of alternative practices as well as for the evaluation of soil indicators and how they react to made changes. Therefore, communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are important components of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.

This document describes the strategic approach of ARTEMIS to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities during the project cycle and is primarily intended as a guide for the project partners. D6.1 will be further developed in line with the overall project work and activities. The main objectives of the communication plan are:

- To **build awareness** and **maximize the impact** of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project among target stakeholders and end-users.
- To **exploit an interest of local communities** for sustainable climate-smart soil management practices.
- To **encourage cooperation** of scientists from soil and soil related disciplines.
- To propose relevant findings **to policy makers to faster implementation** of climate-smart sustainable management practices in Europe.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project will make use of traditional tools, such as scientific and technical papers, press releases, field days, scientific conferences, open days' conferences, Annual Science Days, as well as modern technologies such as webpage and social media channels.

In this document, the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are intended with reference to the guidelines provided by the European Commission (EU Funding & Tenders Portal: Online Manual), as follows:

Communication: the overall communication activities concerns both project activities and results and reach out to a broad audience via website, press releases, newsletters and the use of social media channels (SoMe).

Dissemination: the purpose of dissemination is to communicate outputs and results of the project to potential users, via meetings, policy briefs and scientific papers.

Exploitation: is the uptake of the project results, such as databases, guidelines, visiting researchers, policy or research strategies recommendations, etc.

Stakeholders

Stakeholder engagement improves the relevance of agricultural research and plays an important role in agricultural research adoption.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS communication activities will target all relevant stakeholders and end-users who will be clustered in four broad groups:

- TG1: farmers & advisors (including associations),
- TG2: civil society & general public,
- TG3: the scientific community,
- TG4: policy makers.

Each group will be targeted by specific tools for the provision of specific contents, activating different communication channels: this will help establish the connections and enable a self-standing interaction based on knowledge sharing towards a common goal.

Table 1 The main tools and communication channels targeted at each stakeholder group for the provision of specific content.

Communication and Dissemination Tools/Channels	Objective	Target group	Timeline
Project webpage	Information and knowledge sharing about project aims and partners activities	All target groups	Regularly
Social Media	Awareness creation Outputs presentation	All target groups, especially young generation	Regularly
EJP SOIL Newsletters	Information and Knowledge sharing	TG3, TG4	2 articles
Educational material (leaflets, posters, banners)	Awareness creation Knowledge sharing Outputs presentation	All target groups	As appropriate
Press releases	Awareness creation Knowledge sharing	All target groups	At least 1 official press release per project country
Publications in professional magazines	Awareness creation Knowledge diffusion Outputs presentation	TG1, TG3, TG4	As appropriate, based on project development
Workshops and field days	Provide technical content and relevant information that can be applied on the field	TG1, TG3, TG4	1 joint workshop/field day
	Knowledge sharing To relevant scientific community	TG3	2 Meta-analysis workshops
Webinar and Policy Events	Awareness creation Knowledge sharing Outputs presentation	TG1, TG3, TG4	1 joint webinar
Scientific articles and conferences	Dissemination of relevant results to cover knowledge gaps	TG3	As appropriate, based on project development

Specification of activities

The communication and dissemination activities will be supported by participatory research approach with direct engagement of stakeholders at local, regional, and national level. The success of these activities will depend on the visibility given to EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project in General Media and Social Media as well.

Recently, the use of Social Media by researchers is expanding. Moreover, Social Media has been used in improving the design of public policy. The communication strategy of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project will be focused on Social Media engagement to promote a better information flow and knowledge exchange on sustainable climate-smart soil management practices. Farmers and farmer's associations make use of various Social Media. However, there are still many farmers which are more conservative and lack of IT skills. Field days and workshops are an important source of information and influence farmers' learning and decision-making. To ensure optimum dissemination of outputs, the project will provide educational material (posters, leaflets) to all target stakeholders groups (farmers, advisors, policy makers, researchers, universities, schools, etc.). The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project will be also publicized at scientific conferences and meetings with policy makers.

The clear identification of ARTEMIS and the proper reference to EJP SOIL will be ensured in all types of dissemination activities by using logos and templates according to the dissemination kit provided by the EJP SOIL WP9, whenever EJP SOIL and ARTEMIS will be represented in writing, online, at meetings, at external conferences, workshops etc. Logos and templates have been uploaded to the project repository on Microsoft Teams.

Website

The ARTEMIS webpage will be opened as a subpage of the EJPSOIL portal within 6 months from the project start, and will be regularly updated with project information and all ARTEMIS dissemination materials collected from the project partners.

The webpage will have open access and will contain a section with general information about the project, including maps, work packages, tasks and partners.

The main sections of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage will include the following:

- **Project objectives.** This part will include an overview of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project aims, keywords and coordinators' contacts.
- **Working plan.** This space will contain a short description of each of the 6 Work Packages that compose the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.
- **Project leaders and partners.** This will include the list of project partners and webpage link. Clicking on webpage links leads to a general description of each partner and includes a direct access to its webpage.
- **Introductory video.** The video will provide the main objectives and key takeaways of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.
- **News.** This part will be the repository of all the news related to the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS sub-webpage will be maintained during the project implementation.

Social Media (SoMe) and general media (GMe)

EJP SOIL ARTEMIS will select appropriate media, tools, and channels to reach the identified stakeholders' groups, share results, knowledge diffusion and awareness creation.

Social Media (SoMe) strategy

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS will develop a Social Media strategy that will act as guideline to outreach all target stakeholders with the special focus on young generation (students, young scientists, young farmers, and advisors).

The strategy will set Social Media objectives as:

- Identifying social networks.
- Establishing target groups.
- Developing a content strategy and event calendar.

The Social Media will be used to promote on regular basis the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project activities and outputs. The posts will be specifically tailored to the platforms and target audiences. Similarly, according to Social Media platform, different types of formats will be displayed (e. g. photos and videos on Twitter).

To accelerate the diffusion of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project activities, partners are expected to make use of their existing Social Media platforms.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project has already opened a Twitter account (@EJPSOIL_Artemis) where project partners post latest project events and actively follow soil-agriculture-related official organisations and platforms such as EJP SOIL, FAO, Agorecology Europe, IFOAM Organics Europe, EIP AGRI, Horizon Europe in order to enrich the Twitter ARTEMIS account content and attract more followers.

Content plan

Every month, a content plan will be prepared that includes news and/or events organized with ARTEMIS members' participation, also following the relevant "days of" (earth day, biodiversity day, soil day, EJPSOIL Annual Science Days, etc...). The content plan will be updated each month and shared with WP6 teams and project coordinators for approval/revisions.

TEXT		VISUAL
Week 1 30 th January - 2nd February	#ARTEMIS #ejpsoil will use data from 12 #Europe field experiments to help #sustainable #land use and #evidencebasedpolicymaking.	
Week 2 6 th - 10 th February	Farmers use several alternative #agroecology practices. Which are the best for #soil health under #climatechange? #Armosamodel is useful tool in assessing an impact of #agricultural practices on #soilecosystemservices	
Week 3 13 th – 17 th February	Kick-off-meeting #EJPSOILARTEMIS is approaching. Wellcome to all #Artemis project partners from 8 #EUcountries	
Week 4 20 th – 24 th February	Do you want to know more what progress soil scientists have made in #ejpsoil research projects? MARK YOUR CALENDAR! 12-16 June 2023 for the third Annual #SoilScience Days in Aachen, Germany!	

General media (GMe) strategy

The project team will seek contact with General Media approaching them with specific outputs of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project that may be of interest to the audience of the respective medium.

Local target groups such as farmers, advisors, farmers associations, and local policy makers will be reached by articles in newspapers and professional magazines. They will aim to share the important EJP SOIL ARTEMIS findings on the best agro-ecological management practices.

The official press releases of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS will help to raise the interest and awareness of the project and will be transferred to press offices at national and European level and EJP SOIL WP9.

Minimally two articles will be submitted for the EJP SOIL newsletter during the life span of the project. The articles will summarize the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS main objectives, ongoing activities and obtained results.

The project will provide educational material (posters, leaflets) to all target stakeholders groups (farmers, advisors, policy makers, researchers, universities, schools, etc.).

Workshops and in-field days

Workshops and field days are valuable opportunities to engage in meaningful partnership and experience exchange during an event. The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS partners will co-organize one workshop or field-day. Practical face-to-face field day will run at innovative lighthouse farms with the scope to build communication channels among farmers and scientists.

The EJP SOIL ARTEMIS will also organize 2 workshops focused on the methods of meta-analysis studies. The workshops will be dedicated to scientists and will be designed to learn how to conduct meta-analysis in a proper way.

Scientific events and publications

Scientific results will be published by specialized journals with high impact, which are one of the most important mechanisms for sharing research findings.

Project partners must ensure open access (online access for any user free of charge) to all peer reviewed scientific publication related to their results.

Participation in conferences is a conventional but effective way of disseminating project results and attracting the attention of the scientists. In the first year, the researchers will attend several key conferences, including attendance to EJP SOIL Annual Science Days

For the year 2023, ARTEMIS researchers are planning to attend the following scientific conferences:

Partner Acronym	Conference name	Presentation and/or poster	Place and Date
CREA	IX Congreso Internacional de Agroecología	Di Bene et al. (2023) Agro-ecological strategies for promoting climate change mitigation and adaptation by enhancing soil ecosystem services and sustainable crop production	Sevilla/ Spain January 2023
LUKE	Northern Europe "4 per 1000" Regional Meeting	Valkama et al. (2023), "Organic farming for carbon sequestration in the Baltic Sea Region"	Helsinki/Finland June 2023
AGROSCOPE	EJP SOIL Annual Science Days	Jarosch et al. (2023) Evaluation on different agroecological principles and how they affect soil properties	Aachen/ Germany June 2023

The list of scientific conferences will be extended according to progressing project results. To support this activity, scientific publications and presentations will be also features on the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS website.

EJP SOIL policy events

To disseminate and promote the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project objectives and findings, project coordinators and/or WP leaders will participate in EJP SOIL policy events.

Acknowledging

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References

Communication your project – Acknowledgement of EU funding, <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=1867972>

EU Grants: HE Programme Guide: V2.0 – 11.04.2022, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

Measures to maximize impact in Horizon Europe, <https://enspire.science/measures-to-maximize-impact-in-horizon-europe/>

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The Communication Plan provides the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project a solid framework and practical tools to maximise the project impact through communication and dissemination.

The main objectives of the Communication Plan and all relevant groups of stakeholders have been defined, as well as the communication channels to reach them.

The communication channels such as website and social media have been set up. Workshops or in-field days will be very good opportunity to disseminate the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project outcomes.

To support the success of the EJP SOIL ARTEMIS project and to build awareness about the best agro-ecological soil practices, the project partners will actively participate in the scientific conferences and EJP SOIL policy event as well.